

St. Joseph Confluence Project, Williams County (41.64808, -84.56440)

Since construction in 2021, the St. Joseph Confluence Project’s primary known nutrient benefit has been its runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source, preventing approximately 0.2 lbs phosphorus export per acre each year. Though the dry conditions in 2024 limited the water and nutrients inputs to the Project, the capacity of soils to sorb phosphate suggests potential to capture relatively large loads of phosphorus if and when received. However, there is no active water level management, and the only major water sources for this Project are the adjacent branches of the St. Joseph River. Most pools at this Project function as floodplain wetlands only briefly (a few days or less) when the branches of the St. Joseph River flood. Otherwise, they hold relatively little water and serve as geographically isolated pools. This Project presents a unique opportunity to compare the nutrient reduction benefit and cost efficiency of converting two different land uses—agricultural and Conservation Reserve Program lands—to wetlands.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has 31 acres of restored wetland, consisting of a northern and a southern pool complex. There are eight wetland pools plus one oxbow wetland, all of which receive flow from surface water runoff throughout the year, and act as floodplain pools when the St. Joseph River branches overflow their banks. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event where the St. Joseph River exceeds its banks and flows into the pools.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmfield Area	Phosphorus Loss Prevented Annually	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
20 acres	0.2 lbs	27 ± 13 lbs

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- The pools at this Project are predominantly built to be quite shallow. Modifications for deeper pools could increase residence time and overall nutrient retention.
- Increasing floodplain wetland connection to the river in terms of number of flood events or volume of water received would potentially increase the nutrient retention function of this land.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.